

Viscometric Studies of Smectite and Kaolinite and of Their Mixtures in Aqueous and Acetone Media

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In non-aqueous medium, aggregation of clay particles is pronounced and it is indicated by viscometry. Two clays having marked difference in viscometric behaviour are smectite and kaolinite. The characteristic decrease of viscosity of kaolinite and the characteristic peak viscosity of smectite were observed in aqueous medium. The variation was also observed in the mixture according to the proportion of the individual clays. In aqueous acetone medium, this peak viscosity of smectite was found at higher percentage of neutralisation. The same features were observed in the case of clays indicating the probable aggregation in aqueous acetone medium.

THE variation of viscosity of hydrogen kaolinite and hydrogen smectite suspensions caused by progressive neutralisation is characteristic of both. Kaolinite shows initial fall followed by almost no change. Smectite however shows sharp rise in viscosity on neutralisation with caustic soda to a maximum followed by a gradual to sharp fall^{1,2}. Thus, smectite shows the characteristic rise of viscosity and the peak indicates^{3,4} the presence of it. Viscometric studies⁵ on the binary mixtures of H-smectite and H-kaolinite in aqueous medium showed their individual characteristics. The possible formation of aggregates of clay particles in aqueous acetone may cause the characteristic difference in viscosity of the individual clays and their mixtures from those obtained in aqueous medium. The present work was carried out to ascertain the viscometric behaviour of H-smectite and H-kaolinite singly and in mixtures in aqueous as well as aqueous acetone media.

Experimental

Preparation of clays :

The two clays, smectite and kaolinite, are chosen as they are widely different in properties. The fraction below two micron was isolated from each of the samples according to the usual procedure⁶. Fine subfractions were obtained by allowing the dispersion to settle for 72 hr at room temp. and siphoning off the material in suspension. The organic matter was separated from clay by treatment with hydrogen peroxide. Free oxides of iron, aluminium and silicon were removed by dithionite-citrate-bicarbonate method. The clays were finally washed with alcohol, dialysed and freed from chloride ion, and stored as aqueous colloidal suspension.

Preparation of H-clay :

Each sample of clay was converted to H-clay by equilibrating with H-resin (Amberlite IR-120) sus-

pension in cellophane bags and replacing the H-resin twice or thrice with fresh samples until the pH of the clay suspensions was constant. H-clays thus prepared were stored in Jena bottles and their colloid contents were determined.

H-Smectite and H-kaolinite were mixed in different proportions and kept for 7 days with occasional stirring. This method holds for the aqueous and the acetone media.

Viscometry :

Viscosities of H-kaolinite and H-smectite suspensions were measured at different degrees of neutralisation with caustic soda with the help of a Cannon-Fenske viscometer having a flow of 190 sec for 5 ml distilled water at 35°. All measurements were carried out at 35°. The flow time with water of the viscometer was occasionally checked. Viscometric measurements for the clay mixtures at different degrees of neutralisation were also made in the same way. The same type of viscometric measurements were carried out in 50 : 50 acetone-water medium in case of both individual clays and their mixtures. The caustic soda used for neutralisation also was taken in aqueous acetone medium.

Results and Discussion

The viscometric studies reveal that H-kaolinite shows an initial fall followed by almost no change. Thus the viscosity neutralisation curves obtained with H-kaolinite also show a small initial fall followed by a flat run upto about 80% neutralisation and hence characterise the clay mineral. Viscosity neutralisation curves of smectite show the characteristic rise of viscosity and a peak, indicating the presence of smectite. The peak viscosity values occur in the range of 68 to 79% neutralisation.

The viscometric studies of the binary mixtures of H-smectite and H-kaolinite in aqueous medium

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showed that viscosities of the mixtures decrease with addition of caustic soda used for neutralisation and then they rise to peak values as was observed in the case of the smectite clays. It has been observed that the height of the maximum gradually increases and the depth of the minimum decreases with increase in the proportion of smectite in the mixtures. The peak values of viscosity, for instance, are 7.59, 7.79, 7.80, 7.86 and 7.90 millipoise, as the content of H-smectite varies from 0.012 to 0.106 %, respectively. The peaks appear at percentage of neutralisation varying from 70 to 85. The initial fall in the viscosity on neutralisation is characteristic of kaolinite while the slow rise in viscosity is caused by the presence of H-smectite. When H-smectite is in smaller proportion in the mixtures, the rise in viscosity on neutralisation is also smaller. The viscosity curves of the binary mixtures of H-kaolinite and H-smectite showed that the influence of H-smectite was quite marked. When the quantity of H-smectite in the binary mixture was proportionately higher the viscosity curves resembled those obtained for single H-smectite suspensions whose colloid contents were the same as those in the binary mixtures. It is revealed from the observations that when colloid contents were 0.059, 0.0826 and 0.106% in the mixtures the peaks observed were at 7.80, 7.86 and 7.90 millipoise. The viscosity neutralisation curves of single H-smectite clay showed that the peak values were at 7.84, 7.85 and 7.89 millipoise with respective colloid contents being the same as those of H-smectite in the mixtures.

The presence of non-aqueous solvent i.e. aqueous acetone (50 : 50) seems to alter the viscometric behaviour in comparison to that obtained in aqueous solution, particularly in the case of H-kaolinite. The peak is characteristic of smectite. X-ray diffraction of kaolinite revealed a small impurity of smectite, whose presence was indicated by viscometric changes in aqueous medium, but was revealed by the peak in aqueous acetone medium (Fig. 1).

The viscosity of H-smectite in aqueous acetone shows a pronounced peak at about the point of

Fig. 2. Viscometric titration curve of H-smectite of the same colloid content in different solvent.

Fig. 1. Viscometric titration curve of H-kaolinite of the same colloid content in different solvent.

TABLE 1—BINARY MIXTURES OF H-KAOLINITE AND H-SMECTITE IN AQUEOUS AND Aq. ACETONE MEDIA

Individual colloid content in g% in the mixture				Viscosity at the peak of the curve in millipoise		Neutralisation at the peak in percentage	
Kaolinite		Smectite		Aqueous	Aq. acetone	Aqueous	Aq. acetone
Aqueous	Aq. acetone	Aqueous	Aq. acetone				
0.085	0.081	0.035	0.036	7.79	9.85	78	96
0.061	0.059	0.059	0.058	7.80	9.87	85	89
0.086	0.035	0.082	0.081	7.86	10.07	70	89

equivalence. By comparing the curves obtained in aqueous system it is noted that the peaks in aqueous acetone medium occur generally at a higher percentage of neutralisation, i.e. at about the point of equivalence (Fig. 2). This difference in viscosity can be attributed to the possible aggregation of clay particles in aqueous acetone. In the mixture of H-smectite and H-kaolinite in aqueous acetone medium, the peak viscosity was obtained at a higher percentage of neutralisation than what was obtained in aqueous medium (Table 1). This may likely be due to aggregate formation of clay particles in the aqueous acetone medium.

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